

ROLE OF PRINCIPALS IN SECONDARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION IN NSUKKA EDUCATION ZONE OF ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the role of Principals in Secondary School administration in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: identify the various roles principals play in secondary schools' administration, ascertain the ways principals establish discipline among students and staff and determine the ways principals enhance the performance of students and staff. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and was carried out in Nsukka Education Zone. It made use of questionnaires as the instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions. The researcher discovered that the major findings are that principals' roles include instructional supervision, planning, discipline enforcement, management of facilities and fund; that establishment of discipline involves rules/regulations, disciplinary committee, assignment of form teacher and appointment of students' functionaries; that enhancement of performance calls for in-service training, carrying teachers along in decision making and positive reinforcement. The researcher concluded that discipline begins with the principals if it is to be enforced to teachers and students through rules and regulations, setting up disciplinary committee and functionaries, and assigning form teachers. Hence the principal must be a role model. It was recommended among other things that All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCORPSS) should always organized training/workshop for principals and principals – to – be.

Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

The Principalship and leadership are synonymous in education. The principal is the cornerstone of the school and plays an important role on development of education programme (Abdikadir, 2013). For Linnenburg and Ornstein (2012), usually each school has a single administrative officer, a principal, who is responsible for the operation of the school. The principal is the highest in the order of importance, who takes a leading role in a drama, the chief person in authority, the most important leader of a school or college. Concurring to the above view, Okoroma

(2016) opines that the leadership of secondary schools in Nigeria is provided by principals. He or she is an experienced teacher, or trained and educated to provide leadership in school administration. He further opined that the principal is the chief executive officer of secondary school who influences the results that are obtainable with available educational resources.

Furthermore, the principal is that major component of school administration on whose ability and skill, personality and professional competence will largely depend the tone and efficiency of the school. In other words, the school is as great as the principal is. As is the principal, so is the school. The principal is the keystone in the arch of school administration. More still, principalship is a well-established position of the chief executive who provides instructional leadership. The principals, being instructional leaders, are at the vantage position to supervise, monitor, assess, evaluate and disseminate current information on educational issues and modern teaching techniques to teachers in order to stimulate them for scholarship and best practices in curriculum delivery. For Onyeike and Nwosu (2018), in Nigeria, principals head secondary education, and such head should have demonstrated quality and the information to accomplish his managerial goals.

The job of principal according to Ramon (2019) can get out of hand first, but skilled principals around the world all share some common traits: managing risks; active listening; priority management; tempering others; delegating more tasks; Acting decisively; motivate changes; communicate clearly; promote visions; educate first/administrate second. Society wants that the principal should be a good leader to be able to inspire those who work under his or her direction. The work of the principal then is to see that parts of the machinery work spontaneously and in harmony and unison – not under an artificial compulsion. His or her role is to give direction that others will follow. Supporting this, Shamaki (2015) opines that the success of any school depends on the ability of the principals in his or her leadership style since he or she is the leader of teachers and students.

The principal is also faced with the Leading function. For Northouse (2010), the leading function is also called facilitating, collaborating or actuating but no matter what it is called, leading entails guiding and influencing people. Being the driving force behind the school programme, the principal needs to proactively mobilize all members of staff, teaching and non-teaching, the governing board, parents and the community towards identifying the school's strength and weakness and take appropriate decision on types of follow-up action required to improve teachers' inputs and students' learning outcomes in the school.

Discipline is another area that the role of the principal extends to. Unfortunately, many overlook the aspect of discipline in order to have greater number and make name in public especially in areas of external examination by allowing misconducts. Udemé (2013) is of the view that indiscipline behaviour appears to be endemic in schools in recent times, being manifested by students at all levels particularly among the secondary school students. For him, the social problem of juvenile delinquency which is the main cause of indiscipline has eaten deep into the fabrics of the society like a cankerworm and there is need for something to be done to rid the society of this cankerworm. Other causes may include: bad school management, poor staffing, lack of adequate facilities and unwholesome advertisement which are capable of corrupting the morals of the young ones. Indiscipline has led to withdrawal or expulsion of some students, hence, about 13.5% (boys) and 4.5% (girls) of the students leave school on themselves in fear or are expelled because of these cases of indiscipline. (Mudemb, 2013). However, principals have great tasks in this regard. Derrick (2019) opines that a large part of any school principal's job is to handle students' discipline. The first step, he says, of having effective students' discipline is to ensure that teachers know the expectations. He maintains that discipline starts with you (the enforcer).

From the variables explored, it is clear that when proper roles are played by the principals of secondary schools, the expected outcome or objectives of secondary education are achieved and such schools become successful. However, certain areas of importance were left unaddressed by earlier scholars. Some of those areas include: cure

of indiscipline, pre-service training for would-be principals, proximity of residence of principals to their schools etc. These gaps will be looked at in the discussion of this study but before then, we shall be looking at the context from which this study emanates.

The context of this study therefore lies on the rate of indiscipline noticed in the public secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. This results from the neglect in playing the necessary roles by the principals who are the executive heads of secondary schools. Asako (2015) has it that principals' managerial performances in secondary schools in South-South Nigeria has remained questionable and he opined that evidences abound for poor infrastructure, teachers' poor attitude to work due to vacillating nature of principals like nagging, and non-involvement of teachers in decision making. Hence, indiscipline among staff and students are not uncommon. Even though teachers, parents, ministry of Education share in the blame, the principal carries the greater lot of the blame because they stand as the hub of education. Therefore, this is a very big problem facing education not only in Nsukka education zone but beyond even though our focus will be delimited to Nsukka Education zone.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is quite unfortunate that despite the efforts made by the Federal and State Governments in bringing out objectives of secondary education, what one sees now is never anything impressive or something to write-home about. One of the objectives bordered on raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under Nigerian broad national goals and live as good citizens. A look at what is obtainable now both on those presently undergoing secondary education and the recent products of secondary education shows that this has not been met as it borders on discipline. There is a lot of undisciplined acts portrayed by both the staff and the students which has led to reduction in standard of education and expectations on school learners thereafter. Lack of knowledge, inexperience and negligence on the side of principals as regards their roles in administration of their schools have caused a whole lots of indiscipline and poor performance of students and staff equally. Every year, the society experiences cases of cultism, disregard for teachers/elders, vandalization of facilities in the school, examination misconduct and other nonchalant attitudes from students and some teachers and as such, Mudemb (2013) shows that about 13.5% (boys) and 4.5% (girls) of the students leave school on themselves in fear or are expelled because of these cases of indiscipline. How indiscipline will be curbed, pre-service training for would-be principals for proper knowledge of their role as well as living within or near the school premises were not addressed by scholars, hence, they have contributed to the problem of today. This study tends to proffer a solution to this problem. It is against this background that this study seeks to determine roles of principals in secondary school administration in Nsukka Education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the roles principals play in secondary school administration in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study's objectives are to:

1. Identify the various roles principals play in secondary schools' administration.
2. Ascertain the ways principals establish discipline among students and staff.
3. Determine the ways principals enhance the performance of students and staff.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What are the various roles of principals in secondary school administration?
2. In which ways do principals establish discipline among students and staff?
3. What are the ways principals enhance the performance of students and staff?

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Role of Principal

Before we look at what the roles of principals are, it will make sense clarifying the concept of principal. In America, the term principal is used for the supervisory head of school. The principal of a secondary school is seen as the chief executive who provides instructional leadership and is responsible for the general administration of the secondary school. Onyeike (2018) sees the principal as the custodian and book keeping officer of their various institutions. The principal is the first citizen of the school as well as the chief executive of the school and the chief communication and public relations officers.

Role has to do with the position or purpose that someone or something has in a situation, organization, society or relationship. Here, when we talk of the role of principal, we refer to those sets of connected behaviours, rights, obligations, beliefs and norms as conceptualized by people in the social situation precisely, the school system expected of the principals in running a school for achievement of the goals. Obi (2010) noted that in the age of enlightenment, ignorance relative to the rights, duties and obligations of school administrator may no doubt be costly if not disastrous to the individual, the educational system and others within the school environment. By implication, the roles should be specific and known. Some of them are discussed below.

The principals are tasked with the role of instructional leadership. Shaked, Glanz and Gross (2018) observed that, practically, instructional leadership reflects the actions taken by a principal to promote students leaning and academic success. Present-day school principals are expected to become instructional leaders, facilitating the improvement of teaching and learning (Hallinger & Wang, 2015). In giving a support to this serious role as being paramount, Murphy and Torre (2014) equally opined that scholars contend that contemporary school principals should enact instructional leadership as one of their core responsibilities. The importance lies in the fact that research has discovered a linkage between principals' instructional leadership and their students' achievement (Glickman, Gordon & Ross-Gordon, 2014).

Other roles include: Educational supervision which, for Yunus (2012), is a dynamic process in education aimed at improving the quality of teaching and learning. Then again, handling of students' discipline which according to Derrick (2019) is achieved by ensuring that first, it begins from the enforcer, and secondly, seeing that teachers know their expectations is a role principal play. Another is finance manager/accounting officer (Ogbonnaya, 2010); school climate provider (Waweru & Orodho, 2014) etc. Generally, we can say that the role of principal includes the task of planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, staffing, directing, reporting and budgeting.

2.1.2 School Administration

Administration is the act of administering; government of public affairs; the service rendered, or duties assumed, in conducting affairs. To administer or manage has to do with harnessing both human and material resources available for the achievement of goal. Administration has four important features: manipulation of certain operation; goal oriented; collective/cooperative human effort; and decision making done at the top. Some concepts in administration include decision making, management by objective (MBO) planning, programming and budgeting system (PPBS), scientific management movement, administrative management. School administration has to do with how the human and material resources responsible for the attainment of school goals are harnessed (Udor, 2015).

Some factors that may hinder successful administration of schools include: lack of qualification and experience; inadequate funding; lack of facilities; Poor Staffing; lack of cooperation between the principal and teachers. There are numerous other problems but we shall be limiting them to these ones above as we go on to look at the theories that this study will be hinged on.

2.1.3 Discipline

Discipline is a controlled behaviour, an enforced compliance or a systematic method of obtaining obedience. It has been pointed out earlier that a large part of any school principal's job is to handle staff and students' discipline. When principals perform highly in their tasks, discipline becomes the fruit ripped. But if not, indiscipline, which is seen as a problem in secondary schools (Eke, 2018) and a cankerworm, will invariably affect the quality of teaching and learning, uncovered/unfinished school curriculum. The effect will lead to poor results, dropouts, wastage of resources invested by stakeholders of education such as parents and the government.

In maintaining discipline in schools, Nzoka and Orodho (2014) observe that guidance and counselling becomes a good way because, students make choices in life reasonably and independently. However, when improperly handled, discipline infractions distract the class, throw lesson off schedule, and negatively impact teacher-student relationship (Meador, 2019). The society gets the effect also when not handled properly. It is the thrust of this work, therefore, to create the awareness of the vital role of maintaining discipline among teachers and students on the part of the principal.

2.1.4 Performance

Performance can be understood as the act of performing, carrying into execution or action; as well as the amount of useful work accomplished as estimated in terms of time needed and resources used. Principal's performance, for Ibukun (2011), is seen as the rate or frequency at which they carry out their daily functions towards the attainment of educational goals. High performance of principals' tasks will lead to discipline and overall improvement in the teaching and learning process in the school system. Orodho (2014) sees a relationship between educational management and students' academic performance. This is also supported by Onyeike and Nwosu (2018) who opined that principals' role performance to a great extent determine the effectiveness of the teachers in the performance of their job. Such high performance in teachers can be achieved when principals spur them through intrinsic motivating factors like nature of work, recognition, responsibilities (Ejike, 2011).

FRN (2014) outlined that among the roles of principals in administering secondary schools is the role of providing effective managerial skills and styles (performance) which will enhance better job performance among teachers that could enhance students' academic performance. How effective the principal is in performing these roles according to Fika, Ibi and Aji (2015) has been a matter of concern to many educationists. To this, this present study tries to determine the extent principals enhance the performance of teachers and students.

2.2 Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is anchored on the System Theory.

2.2.1 System Theory

The system theory was propounded by a German Biologist Ludwig Von Bertalanffy in the year 1954. For him, there exist models, principles, and laws that apply to generalized systems or their subclasses, irrespective of their component elements, and the relationships or "forces" between them. It seems legitimate to ask for a theory, not of systems of a special kind, but of universal principles applying to systems in general. He asserted that a system is like model developed which starts with the input, which is processed over different stages until the output is obtained. System theory can be defined as an entity composed of a number of parts, the relationships of these parts and the attributes of both the parts and the relationship. A system as computer – related technology was introduced in organizations, a new approach which is known as the "system approach" began to emerge. This theory claims that an organization consists of a number of sub-systems and whatever happens to one sub-system affects the whole system.

A lot of strengths have been recorded on this theory. The strength lies in the interdependency, adaptability, and exchange of resources energy from the different systems. For instance, in dynamic system theory, there is an

emphasis on removing obstacles in the system like institutional racism as a barrier for people of colour. It also focuses on inclusion rather than separation, and a connectedness to all living things on earth, even earth itself. System theory was later furthered by Reigeluth, Bathany, and Olson in the year 1993 when they talked about system view. For them, a system view suggests that essential quality of a part resides in its relationship to the whole; the system and its parts should be designed from the perspective of the whole system and in view of its embeddedness in its environment; and that the systems design notion requires both coordination and integration. Ashby (1957) concept of Cybernetics was also built on the foundation of system theory.

System theory is not immune from limitations or weaknesses. The limitations of the system theory lie in structural functionalism theory. This theory places emphasis on the homeostasis. It only agrees with changes that stabilize the system. This can pose a problem when presented with problems such as racism, LGBTQ (lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer), and the poor. Again, through this theory, only slow and steady change can occur rather than radical changes. With regard to the impact of the theory on education system or its link to this study, it is noted that, systematic change recognizes the interrelationships and interdependencies among the parts of education system, with the consequence that desired changes in one part of the system are accompanied by changes in other parts that are necessary to support those desired changes. It also recognizes the interrelationship and interdependencies between the educational systems and its community. By implication, principals will do their best in coordinating the entire system (the learning experience subsystem, the instructional subsystem, the administrative subsystem, and the governance subsystem) without neglecting any area or leaving it undisciplined. Hence this theory is linked to this study in the sense that negligence in any aspect of the school part, be it curriculum, discipline, structural will certainly affect the other systems and so, principals should through delegation of function and supervision, see to it that all aspects of the school are carried along. When applied well, it will provide the organization (school) and its leaders a holistic approach to view the complete value chain and the impact of the organization in creating a favourable environment in which to achieve the stated goals.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ugwu (2009) conducted a research on delegatory functions of secondary school principals in all the public secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone using a descriptive survey research design. 441 staff and the whole 59 principals were used for the study using a simple random sampling. Three research questions and two null hypotheses were used and questionnaire titled “Delegatory Functions of Secondary School Principals (DEPQ)” was used in gathering data for the study. The statistical tools used for answering the research questions were mean, and standard deviation while student T-test statistics was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and staff with regard to the extent principals delegate functions to their staff and how they control delegated functions in the school. The educational implication is that delegating duties helps the principals to cover the whole areas awaiting his attention. This research is related to the present study on the aspect of considering delegation as a function or role of the principal and for the fact that it is the same education zone but differs from it as it based on delegation.

Renuka, Vusi, and Onoriode (2015) carried out a research on Leadership Role of School Principals in Democratic Schools in South Africa: Case Studies of Two Schools. This paper reports on a qualitative case study located within interpretative paradigm. This study aimed at understanding the role of school principals in leading and managing democratic schools. Towards that, semi-structured interviews were used to obtain data from research participants. Purposive sampling was used to meet the purpose of this study. In sum, eight participants were selected for the study. The findings of the study reveal that leadership is a major role of principals in democratic schools, as it

also extended to others in the school community. This has educational implication in the sense that assuming the position of leaders, principals will play their roles properly. Hence, the present study has a relationship with it as it clarifies the principal as a leader but goes beyond to cover the gap created by limiting the roles of principals to only leaders, incorporating other numerous roles such as maintaining discipline, providing a good school climate, delegation, planning, coordinating, budgeting etc.

Onyeike and Nwosu (2018) conducted a research on principals 'administrative and supervisory roles for teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided their study. Descriptive survey was adopted while the population of the study was 8452 teachers of secondary schools in the state. The sample size of 265 teachers which represented 3.1% of the entire population was drawn through cluster sampling technique. A questionnaire titled principal's administrative and supervisory role for teachers' job effectiveness questionnaire (PASTJEQ) was developed and used for data collection. Measures of central tendency; mean, mean set, standard deviation and rank order statistics were used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Z-test statistics. The findings among others were as follows: principals engage in staff personnel administration and providing assistance on instructional activities to teachers in Rivers State. The educational implication is such that the principals should maintain supervisory role as a way of leading the school. The study is related to this research considering supervisory role as part of the roles of principals but differ from it from the point that the purpose is on teachers' effectiveness. It was also conducted in another state. It therefore closed the gap of considering only an aspect of the school components.

Barongo (2016) conducted a research on School Administration Strategies and Students' Discipline in Public Secondary Schools in Kisii Central District, Kenya. It was done at Kisii University, Kenya. The research was guided by four objectives which included: To establish how the Principals' use of democratic leadership influences students' discipline in public secondary schools, to determine the extent to which the Principals' means of communication influence students' discipline in public secondary schools, to examine how the involvement of prefects' body in decision making process affects students' discipline in public secondary schools. The researcher applied descriptive survey research design. This is because the design was useful since it collected data from members of the population in order to determine the current status without manipulating the variables. The target population consisted of all 52 public secondary schools in Kisii Central District, 52 Principals and 1,560 teachers in the administration of the school affairs. Simple random sampling was used in selecting teachers at school level from the 16 Principals and 30 teachers per school who participated. Data were gathered by use of questionnaires and analysed using quantitative method in frequency distribution tables, percentages and bar graphs. The findings showed that principals use democratic leadership style, communication techniques as well as involvement of prefects' body on behalf of all students in decision making process as strategies for maintaining discipline. The educational implication is such that when principals use democratic method, establish communication means as well as involves the students' council in decision making in school, discipline will be achieved. This study is related to the above research on the aspect that it sought out how discipline is maintained by principals but differs from it because it looked at discipline from the perspective of the principal's role. Also, it is different, from the fact that it is being carried out from a different site/country.

Omemu (2017) carried a research on Relationship between Principals Administrative Strategies and Student Disciplinary Problems in Secondary School, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between administrative strategy by principals and their effectiveness in tackling disciplinary problems. Three research questions were asked and one hypothesis was raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Ninety-five randomly selected principals from Bayelsa State constitute the sample. The instrument for the study is made up of three

parts—first part is biodata of the respondents; second part solicits information on administrative strategy, while the third part solicits information on disciplinary problems. It has a test re-test validity. The r-value for this instrument is 1.96. This measures internal consistency. The findings reveal a significant relationship between principal's administrative strategy and their effectiveness in handling disciplinary problems. It also shows that there is a significant relationship between Administrative Strategy and their assessment of students' behavioural outcomes. Its educational implication shows that the principals ought to adopt strategies in their roles for maintaining discipline. This study considered also principals' role in attaining discipline however, it considered beyond discipline to other roles.

Ńzokurum and Iremeka (2017) researched on Students' Discipline Management, Personnel Services and Teachers' Productivity in Public Secondary Schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study investigated extent students discipline management and personnel services contributes to teachers' productivity in senior secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. Two research questions with two null hypotheses in line with two objectives guided the study. The study adopted a correlation research design. The sample of the study comprised all the 291 principals (211 males and 80 females) in the 17 LGA of Enugu State. The purposive sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample size. Two self-designed instruments titled "Principal Students' Discipline and Personnel Management Scale" (PSDPMS) and "Teacher Productivity Questionnaire" (TPQ) were used to collect data. Face and content validities of the instruments were ensured. The reliability of PSDPMS is given at 0.79 while TPQ was given at 0.82 respectively using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Linear regression coefficient of determinism was used to answer the research questions while t-test associated with linear regression was used to answer the null hypotheses. It was found among others that, the principals' provision of students discipline contributes only 6.1% of teachers' productivity in senior secondary schools in Enugu State while 93.9% is contributed by some other factors. Its educational implication is that, among other things, Students' attitude towards education should be developed by the principals and teachers through incentives and rewards on acceptable behaviours in order to enhance teachers' productivity to a great extent in secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. This study agrees with it that achievement is not only determined by discipline.

Lokuruka and Ronoh (2017) conducted a research on The Role of Head Teachers in the Management of the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Turkana County, Kenya. The objective of this study was to examine the role of Head Teachers in the management of the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education performance in public secondary schools in Turkana County. The study adopted descriptive survey design with a total of 160 teachers selected from 16 public secondary schools. The instrument was tested in three public secondary schools and a reliability coefficient of 0.7 was obtained. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. The study findings suggested that to improve performance; availability of teaching and learning resources, good teacher-head teacher working relationship, teacher quality and consultative decision-making process should be enhanced. The educational implication lies on the fact that both management and resources must be adequately available and utilized. This study relates to it on the ground that it is the School-heads' role to manage resources. It covered the gap of limiting the roles to relationship and resource management.

3.0 Methodology

The research design for this study was descriptive survey research design. It was targeted at providing the opinions of the respondents on what the role of principals are in the administration of secondary schools of Nsukka education zone. The study was carried out in Nsukka education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. This education zone comprises of three local government areas, namely; Igbo Etiti, Nsukka and Uzo-Uwani local government areas. This Education Zone is the surrounding place of the northern part of Enugu State (southern part of Nigeria), the home site of the famous University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) and shares boundary with Kogi and Anambra

States. The population of the study comprises of all the 61 principals of the 61 public secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone {Source: Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB) Nsukka planning research and statistical unit (2018/2019)}. The sample size of the study is 53. This sample was determined using the formula: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$, where n= sample size, N=Population, 1=constant and e= Error term or Significant level (0.05) as was recommended by Taro Yamane (1967). This sample comprises 53 of the total population of 61 principals selected from the secondary schools using simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents, which included 53 principals, directly. The responses for each item of the research question were tallied and weighted using 4-point rating scale. The total weighted frequencies were used to determine the mean score for each item. Mean score from 2.50 was considered acceptable while any mean score below 2.50 was considered rejected. The mean and the standard deviation were used to analyse the five research questions posed for the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT PRESENTATION

Research Question One

What are the various roles of principals in secondary school administration?

Table 1- Cluster A: Mean and Standard Deviation of Various Roles of Principals in Secondary School Administration

S/N	Items	N = 53	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
1	Principal supervises instruction in classes.		3.47	0.36	A
2	Principal plans, organises and coordinates school activities.		3.79	0.62	A
3	Principal gives information about the school to the community.		3.21	0.43	A
4	Principal enforces discipline and maintains standards in school.		3.70	0.58	A
5	Principal manages school facilities and accounts for fund meant for the development of the school.		3.34	0.51	A
Grand Mean			3.50	0.50	A

Key: N = Number of Subjects, \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec = Decision, A = Accepted & R = Rejected

The grand mean response score of 3.50 with its associated standard deviation 0.50 which is above the mean rating bench mark of 2.50 indicated that respondents agreed with the five items under cluster A as roles of principals in secondary school administration.

Research Question Two

In which ways do principals establish discipline among students and staff?

Table 2- Cluster B: Mean and Standard Deviation of Principals' Discipline among Students and Staff

S/N	Items	N = 53	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
6	Principal is a role model to staff and students.		3.68	0.61	A
7	Principal sets up framework for discipline (rules and regulations) among staff and students.		3.38	0.62	A
8	Principal constitutes disciplinary committee that recommends disciplinary measures on staff and students		3.53	0.53	A
9	Principal assigns classes to form teachers to maintain order and decorum in class.		3.68	0.68	A
10	Principal appoints students' functionaries to help maintain discipline among students.		3.02	0.31	A
Grand Mean			3.46	0.55	A

Key: N = Number of Subjects, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec = Decision, A = Accepted & R = Rejected

The grand mean response score of 3.46 with its associated standard deviation 0.55 which is above the mean rating bench mark of 2.50 indicated that **respondents** agreed with the five items under cluster B as principals' established discipline among students and staff in secondary schools.

Research Question Three

What are the ways principals enhance the performance of students and staff?

Table 3 - Cluster C: Mean and Standard Deviation of Principals' Performance Enhancement

S/N	Items	N = 53	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
11	Principal provides professional training and workshops for teachers.		2.72	0.58	A
12	Principal motivates teachers and involves them in decision making process.		3.52	0.65	A
13	Principal communicates his or her expectations of teachers and students.		3.25	0.59	A
14	Principal uses positive reinforcement on teachers and students.		3.57	0.63	A
15	Principal provides quality teachers and facilities for students' academic performance.		2.55	0.48	A
Grand Mean			3.12	0.59	A

Key: N = Number of Subjects, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec = Decision, A = Accepted & R = Rejected

The grand mean response score of 3.12 with its associated standard deviation 0.59 which is above the mean rating bench mark of 2.50 indicated that respondents agreed with the five items under cluster C as principals' Performance Enhancement strategies in secondary schools.

Summary of Findings

The results of the analysis presented above showed the following findings:

1. Supervision of instruction, planning, discipline enforcement and management of facilities and funds are various roles of principal in administration of secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone.
2. Establishment of rules and regulations, disciplinary committee, assignment of form teachers and appointment of students' functionaries are the major ways principals can establish discipline in secondary schools.
3. Encouraging in-service training, carrying teachers along in decision making and positive reinforcement are principal's way of enhancing students and staff performance.

Conclusion

Principals' roles are multifaceted and include among others: supervision of instructions; planning, organization and coordination of activities; communication with the host community; discipline and standard enforcement; and facilities management and fund accountability. Discipline begins with the principals if it is to be enforced to teachers and students through rules and regulations, setting up disciplinary committee and functionaries, and assigning form teachers. Hence the principal must be a role model. Provision of professional training for teachers and quality teachers for students, carrying staff and students along by communicating his/her expectations and involvement of them in decision making will enhance performance by the principal among staff and students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following;

1. All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCORPSS) should always organized training/workshop for principals and principals – to – be.
2. The State Government should help in funding the secondary schools to minimize the constraints faced in administration.
3. The Enugu State Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB) should post qualified and required teachers to schools as well as provide necessary structures and facilities to schools.

References

- Abdikadir, I. F. (2013). School management characteristics of effective principal. *Global Journal of Social Science Linguistics and Education*, 13(13), 22–49.
- All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCORPSS). (2016). *Principals year book*. Nsukka: Mike Social Publishers.
- Ashby, W. R. (1957). *An introduction to cybernetics*. London: Chapman & Hall LTD.
- Barongo, S. (2016). School administration strategies and students' discipline in public secondary schools in Kisii Central District, Kenya. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(11), 1–10. <https://www.iiste.org>
- Derrick, M. (2019). The role of principals in schools. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/role-of-principal-in-secondary-schools-3194583> (Accessed May 2, 2020)
- Ejike, N. O. (2011). *Teachers motivation and job satisfaction in schools of nursing in South-East, Nigeria* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Eke, G. J. (2018). Indiscipline in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area in Bayelsa State. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(5), 1–13.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2014). *National policy on education* (6th ed.). Lagos: NERDC.
- Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (2014). *Supervision and instructional leadership: A developmental approach* (9th ed.). London: Pearson.
- Ibukun, O. A. (2011). Principal leadership effectiveness. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 5(2), 472–479. <http://www.recentscientific.com>
- Lokuruka, N. J., & Ronoh, R. K. (2017). The role of head teachers in the management of the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education performance in public secondary schools in Turkana County, Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 7(2), 68–75.
- Mudemb, E. V. (2013). *Causes of dropout among boys and girls from secondary schools in Ugenya District, Siaya County, Kenya* (Master's dissertation, University of Nairobi).

- Murphy, J., & Torre, D. (2014). *Creating productive cultures in schools: For students, teachers and parents*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
- Northouse, P. G. (2010). *Leadership: Theory and practice* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Nzoka, J. T., & Orodho, A. J. (2014). School management and students' performance: How effective are strategies being employed by Embu North District, Embu County, Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(9), 86–99.
- Obi, E. (2010). *Laws and education management*. Enugu: Empathy International.
- Okoroma, N. S. (2016). Administrative abilities of male and female principals and goals achievement in Nigerian public secondary schools. *Journal of Culture, Society and Development*, 20(6), 1–36.
- Omemu, F. (2017). Relationship between principals' administrative strategies and student disciplinary problems in secondary schools, Bayelsa State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(5), 100–104.
- Onyeike, V. C., & Nwosu, C. M. (2018). Principals' administrative and supervisory roles for teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. *British Journal of Education*, 6(6), 38–49.
- Orodho, A. G. (2014). Coalescing nutrition and health programmes to enhance pupils' participation in basic education as a panacea to socio-economic development of marginalized communities in Kenya in the 21st century. Paper presented at the African Nutrition Conference, North Coast Beach Hotel, Mombasa, Kenya.
- Ramon, C. (2019). Top 10 skills every school principal must have. Pikmykid. <https://www.pikmykid.com/top-10-skills-every-school-principal-must-have> (Accessed May 5, 2020)
- Shaked, H., Glanz, J., & Gross, Z. (2018). Gender differences in instructional leadership: How male and female principals perform their instructional leadership role. *Journal of School Leadership and Management*, 38(4), 417–434.
- Shamaki, E. B. (2015). Influence of leadership style on teacher's job productivity in public secondary schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(10), 200–204.
- Udeme, A. U. (2013). Indiscipline, parenting style and attitude to learning of students in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(5), 87–92.
- Udor, U. O. E. (2015). Effective administration of secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria: A panacea for academic excellence. *Science Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 2015(214), 1–3.
- Ugwu, L. C. (2009). *Delegatory function of secondary school principals in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State* (Unpublished master's dissertation). University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

Waweru, P. N., & Orodho, A. D. (2013). Management practice and students' academic performance in national examinations in public secondary schools in Kiambu County. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332761302-Gender-difference-in-Instructional-Leadership-how-male-and-female-principals-perform-their-instructional-leadership-role>